

OPPORTUNITIES TO PREPARE FUTURE TEACHERS TO DIAGNOSE AND ASSESS STUDENT DEVELOPMENT LEVELS

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Diagnosis is considered as the assessment practice of a future teacher. It serves to identify the unique psychological characteristics of students and the social qualities of the student group. When choosing diagnostic methods, the future teacher should consider a number of characteristics:

- the age characteristics of the students in the class;
- the level of formation of the group of students in the class and its specific characteristics;
- specific aspects of interaction between pedagogues and students;
- it is important to take into account the mutual trust levels of teachers and students as well as students and students.

Future teachers should acquire the experience of following specific rules presented below in the process of acquiring the competence of using methods of diagnosis and assessment of students' development levels:

1. The content of diagnostic methods should correspond to the intended result.
2. The diagnosis has its own specific content and creates favorable opportunities for the future teacher to carry out research activities.
3. Knowing that the results of the diagnosis will not be discussed by students and persons not related to the educational process.
4. To make them realize that the results of diagnosis and evaluation serve the development of students in the class and help them to eliminate conflicts between students.
5. To be able to imagine that the results of the diagnosis will serve to correct the gaps in the students' activity and ensure their future development levels.
6. Knowing that the results of pedagogical diagnosis serve to clearly demonstrate the characteristics of each student.

Future teachers should have the competence to use the following methods in order to diagnose and evaluate the development levels of students in the classroom. They are:

- observation of students' learning activities in natural learning environments;
- to study the students' actions, behavior, and their work, using the method of observing the conflicts that arise between them;
- ensure that questionnaires create motivation for students to perform positive actions;
- to study the activity motives, interests and needs of students and groups of students, to make a comprehensive analysis;
- studying the levels of students' anxiety in the classroom and its causes, and looking for measures to eliminate it;
- determine students' attitudes to certain problems and events;
- using questionnaires to study the impact of the same student on the group of students and the group of students on a specific student;

- study of the student's relationship to the student body, teacher and parents based on drawings and models within the framework of the diagnostic methodology.

In order to ensure the development of students in the classroom, future teachers are required to master the methods of establishing cooperation with school psychologists and social pedagogues in the process of higher pedagogical education. In order to ensure the development level of students, it is necessary to pay special attention to the content of activities and interpersonal relations that are carried out in cooperation with them.

It is important to form motives for students to study and be interested in the learning process. Future teachers, realizing this at the right time, are required to thoroughly master the method of organizing questionnaire surveys among students. It is of particular importance that they contact students using questionnaires with the following contents.

1. Are you interested in learning and acquiring knowledge?
2. Why do you like coming to school?
3. Do you want to stay at home?
4. What classes do you not want to miss?
5. What do you do in your spare time?
6. If the teachers said that only those who wanted to could come to school, would you stay home or go to school?
7. Do you like to do homework, with whom do you do it?
8. Do you tell your parents about your schoolwork?
9. Do you want your teacher to be strict and demanding?
10. Do you have many friends in class, are they girls or boys?
11. What clubs would you like to join?
12. What do you do outside of class?

It can be seen that such students face certain difficulties in acquiring knowledge and information during the educational process. They can master the learning materials well. However, they face difficulties in communication with classmates and teachers. They are reluctant to express their thoughts clearly and concisely. They have conflicts with most of the students in the class. They rush to go home before the class ends.

In some cases, they have different pressures. As a result, they refuse to do the teacher's assignments. They do not want to follow the rules and regulations. Future teachers should understand that complex processes take place in the psyche of such students, and they should have pedagogical and psychological knowledge in the field of working with them. When we made these students draw pictures, we were able to determine that these pictures are not related to educational topics, but to the experiences of this student, the world of fantasy.

It is required that future teachers separately test their pedagogical and psychological knowledge of working with such students during the practice period. Future teachers need to familiarize themselves with the instructions, guidelines and recommendations for working with the class team during the Higher Pedagogical Education process.

It is recommended that future teachers draw pictures, organize conversations, and establish individual dialogues with students in order to closely study students and diagnose and assess their development levels during pedagogical practice.

They should analyze regularly, paying attention to the sequence, logical consistency, and mutual proportionality of students' actions. For this, future teachers should work more with the

class team during the pedagogical practice, study the characteristics of the students thoroughly. Based on interviews, practical work and descriptions with each student, future teachers need to effectively use methods of diagnosis and assessment of their development levels.

Future teachers will have a clear idea of the level of development of students based on the assessment of tasks completed by students. In addition, it is recommended that students choose tasks that are set before them in accordance with the tasks used in the process of diagnosis and evaluation. These tasks should logically be a continuation of the previously given tasks. It is desirable that future teachers use their visual activity as much as possible in diagnosing and evaluating the development levels of students. Because the students' development levels, thoughts, and experiences are more often expressed in their visual work.

If the students do not complete the assigned task, leave it half way, or are busy with other work instead, the students are required to have the ability to analyze their performance and accurately assess the level of development. In order to assess the development levels of students, it is intended to provide students with the experience of writing specific descriptions for each of them.

Students' developmental levels should be diagnosed and evaluated in relation to their behavior. It is intended to determine the development levels of students through the analysis of conflict situations between them. Future teachers are required to pay special attention to the ability of students to complete tasks independently. Prospective teachers should also pay special attention to their task-related skills and behaviors when diagnosing and assessing students' developmental levels.

In the process of analyzing the performance of tasks, it is recommended to take into account the level of independent approach of students to them.

In diagnosing and evaluating the development levels of students, it is of particular importance that future teachers analyze the performance of each task and introduce it closely to students. In this case, it is important to analyze the levels of students' communication, visual activities, reading skills, independent approach to assignments, and their performance levels. The future teacher should be able to carry out pedagogical activities aimed at choosing tasks that allow to show the unique aspects of each student in order to effectively master the pedagogical experience of diagnosing and evaluating the development levels of students.

Future teachers are required to rely on the topics in the curriculum when choosing tasks, to master the requirements of the program thoroughly. When choosing tasks, future teachers should pay attention to the fact that they have the same level of complexity for all students in the class. It is important for students to identify the mistakes made by themselves and their classmates and correct them independently. When giving tasks to students, it is necessary not to limit their time, but future teachers should be able to control that this time does not exceed 5-7 minutes. During this period, it is important that they are able to observe and identify the specific developmental levels of students.

In the process of completing assignments, future teachers are required to monitor and record students' actions, capabilities, and activity levels.

Future teachers should be ready to mitigate the following situations that arise with students:

- refusing to perform tasks or having a negative attitude towards this process;
- the student becomes depressed or cries from being exposed to some influence;

- expects additional help from the teacher or feels certain pressure in the process of completing tasks;

- showing that he did not understand the topic.

It is important for future teachers to learn the uniqueness of students' behavior in time. The results of the questionnaire surveys conducted with students during the pedagogical practice showed that development motives are clearly manifested in elementary school students. They showed a tendency to acquire more learning materials on time, to perform positive behaviors. Diagnosing and evaluating the development levels of these students did not cause special difficulties in the work of future teachers.

Future teachers paid attention to the following when diagnosing and evaluating the general educational skills, skills, competences, upbringing and social formation levels of students:

- listening to the student;
- to determine whether they have completed their work;
- to study and generalize the theoretical approaches to the development of students and the opinions of members of the pedagogical team;

- regularly thinking about the problem of diagnosing and evaluating the student's development level and making clear conclusions;

- approach with special interest in diagnosis and assessment of students' development levels;

- asking students frequent questions;

- regular development of one's own assessment and diagnosis knowledge, striving to learn new methods;

- regular control and independent assessment of practical-pedagogical activities related to the application of assessment and diagnostic methods;

- conveying one's opinion to students, speaking in a way that is understandable to them;

- treat students and other members of the pedagogical team with respect;

- clearly understanding and taking into account the peculiarities of students and situations related to inclusion;

- feeling responsible for his actions, solutions, decisions;

- believes in the objectivity of his pedagogical knowledge, professional thinking and decisions;

- independence of actions and ensuring that they are carried out within the framework of professional ethics;

- such as being able to demonstrate the ability to positively influence students in the classroom.

Students are expected to focus on the following as a result of mastering knowledge of diagnosing and assessing student developmental levels. We analyzed the answers given by the students of the 3rd and 4th grade to the following questions, summarizing their activities in this direction.

1. What methods of diagnosis and assessment of students' development levels did we learn during the training?

2. What new methods did we manage to use during the pedagogical practice?

3. What conclusions did we come to as a result of observing the students' activities;

4. What important information did we discover?

What rules do we follow when diagnosing and evaluating students' knowledge?

5. Which instructions of professors and teachers did we follow in the diagnosis and assessment of students' development levels?

6. How can methods in the field of diagnosis and evaluation of students' development levels be divided into groups?

7. What did we feel while working with students?

8. Have we followed the rules of mutual respect when engaging in dialogue-based relationships with students?

Future teachers are also required to thoroughly master professional knowledge related to the control of the knowledge and activity methods of students in various educational subjects. Students are required to systematically engage in the correct performance of learning activities aimed at developing professional knowledge, mastering activity algorithms.

Future teachers are expected to pay special attention to mastering systematic methods and methods of working with students. Future teachers should realize that the students who failed to complete the first task clearly have a feeling of self-doubt and fear, and they do not dare to complete the next tasks. It is important that they perform their actions with a specific goal in mind.

In order to determine the level of development of students' motives for learning, it is appropriate for future teachers to observe in the classroom and extracurricular pedagogical processes. In this, they are closely assisted by diagnostic methods. N.G. Luskanova's methodology closely helps students in diagnosing and evaluating students' development levels. This methodology requires analysis of drawn pictures and answers to questions. Therefore, students should be able to use this method effectively during pedagogical practice.

In addition, encouraging students to perform various tasks, monitoring their answers to questions, analyzing the results of their educational activities, determining the levels of socialization also serve to develop the professional competencies of future teachers. The formation of the experience of valuable attitude towards students in future teachers takes place in the following directions:

- formation of social activity among students;
- the formation of a conscious attitude towards the educational process;
- pedagogical work, such as the formation of a professional attitude towards students, their parents and the public.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 28, 2022 No. PF-60 “On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026”.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 No. PF- 134 “ON approval of the national program for the development of public education in 2022-2026”.
3. Aleksashina I.Yu. Учитель и новые ориентиры образования. Monograph. SPb., 1997.- 153p.
4. Borisova N.V. Педагогические условия развития функции само реализации личности старшеклассников в учебно- деловой игре: Diss: ped. Science –Volgograd, 2001.

5. Voroshilov V.V. Organizational and pedagogic conditions of education, pedagogy, methods of project work: Diss... Ped. science –M.,2000.- 149p.
6. Safarova R. G., D.M. Malikova. “Possibilities of organizing the educational process in specialized schools and classes”. Methodical guide. Tashkent.
7. Safarova R.G. “Specific aspects of specialized education and international experiences in this field// Pedagogy. - Tashkent. 2022 No. 1. B. 7-12.